

Supplemental Material

Adaptation and Mitigation Strategies of Port Logistics in the Face of Climate Change

Andreas Mohr¹[0000-0001-8751-4052], Shubhangi Gupta¹[0009-0003-3574-2899], Yann Kinkel¹[0009-0007-9408-8144], Simon Ilenburg¹[0009-0001-8411-4958], Ann-Kathrin Lange¹[0000-0002-1503-1729],
and Carlos Jahn¹[0000-0002-5409-0748]

¹ Hamburg University of Technology, School of Management Sciences and Technology, Institute of Maritime Logistics, Am Schwarzenberg-Campus 4, 21073 Hamburg, Germany,
andreas.mohr@tuhh.de

1 Data Analysis

1.1 Choice of data source

This paper utilizes available data and models published by Copernicus Climate Data Store. Copernicus Data Store is the official European platform from ECMWF to retrieve this information.

1.2 Data sources of hazards

Table 1. GCMs and RCMS used for atmospheric hazards

GCM	RCM	Ensemble member
EC-EARTH	HIRHAM5	r3i1p1
EC-EARTH	RACMO22E	r1i1p1
EC-EARTH	RCA4	r12i1p1
HadGEM2-ES	RACMO22E	r1i1p1
HadGEM2-ES	RCA4	r1i1p1
IPSL-CM5A-MR	WRF381P	r1i1p1
MPI-ESM-LR	CCLM4-8-17	r1i1p1
MPI-ESM-LR	RCA4	r1i1p1
NORES-M1-M	HIRHAM5	r1i1p1

Table 2. GCM and RCMS used for the river and coastal flood hazards

RF50y			CF100y
GCM	RCM	Ensemble member	GCM
HadGEM2-ES	RACMO22E	r1i1p1	CMCC-CM2-VHR4
HadGEM2-ES	RCA4	r1i1p1	EC-Earth3P-HR
MPI-ESM-LR	REMO2009	r1i1p1	HadGEM3-GC31-HM
MPI-ESM-LR	RCA4	r1i1p1	HadGEM3-GC31-HM-SST

1.3 Data Analysis – Hazard Selection

Extreme precipitation (snowfall or rainfall) can cause flooding, environmental pollution, and is threatening the navigability of waterways [1]. Crane operations are suspended when rainfall exceeds certain levels [2]. The index employed is the number of days per year that exceed the extreme threshold, defined by the 95th per-centile of daily precipitation from 1981 to 2010 [3]. Extreme wind conditions can significantly disrupt berthing and loading operations, compromise crane functionality, and threaten the safety of port personnel [1, 4, 5]. The index selected is the number of days above the 10-meter wind speed extreme threshold, defined by the 98th percentile of surface wind speed between 1981 to 2010 [3]. Extreme heat threatens port personnel's health [6], requiring pauses and causes operational downtime [1, 4, 5]. Additionally, extreme heat can induce spontaneous coal fires in ports with coal bulk terminals [1]. As heat index, the number of days with a maximum temperature of 35°C is selected.

Coastal floods can lead to physical impacts on ports and disrupt operations [4, 5]. They are caused by CC through mean sea level rise (MSLR) and changes in extreme sea levels from wave set-ups, tides, and storm surges. These factors are retrieved independently and combined into a total water level index for coastal floods with a 100-year return period. River floods can also lead to port downtimes and destruction of port infrastructure [4, 5, 7]. Currently, over one-fifth of global ports are affected by fluvial floods [5]. CC is changing the patterns of European river floods, causing variability frequency and intensity of these events [8]. To assess the CC-related changes in river floods in ports, the intensity of 50-year floods is selected as index.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Search String

applied on June 27, 2025:

(TITLE-ABS-KEY ((port or harbor or harbour or maritime) and (logistic* or transport or shipping))

AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (climate or "climate change" or green or sustainab* or weather or "extreme weather" or "weather events" or "carbon footprint" or "carbon emission")

AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (mitigation or mitigating or adaptation or adapting or readiness or reduction or reducing)

AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (equipment or infrastructure or process* or operation*))

2.2 SLR Procedure

Fig. 1. Procedure of the systematic literature review

2.3 Reports used in different sections

Table 3. References used in the specific paragraph

Section	Paragraph	References used
Mitigation	Introduction	15, 30, 35, 47, 60
	Infrastructure and Energy	1, 3, 5, 6, 10, 11, 14, 20, 24, 26, 27, 31, 33, 37, 39, 43, 48, 50, 59, 53, 55, 57, 59, 60, 62
	Management and Operations.	3, 4, 13, 16, 18, 19, 22, 39, 41, 45, 48, 49, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 63
	Laws and Regulations	2, 3, 28, 32, 35, 37, 38, 48, 54, 55, 56, 59, 60
	Finance and Politics	15, 48, 49, 53
Adaptation	Introduction	17, 30 64
	Resilience	7, 8, 17, 23, 44, 52, 64
	Management and Operation	7, 17, 18, 27, 30, 35, 44, 52
	Finance and Politics	7, 35, 44, 59, 64

Publication	qty	Mitigation									Adaptation								
		G	I	E	M	O	L	R	F	P	D	G	I	M	O	D	R	F	P
[33]	1																		
[34]	3																		
[35]	14																		
[36]	5																		
[37]	5																		
[38]	2																		
[39]	2																		
[40]	1																		
[41]	2																		
[42]	1																		
[43]	1																		
[44]	18																		
[45]	1																		
[46]	1																		
[47]	1																		
[48]	11																		
[49]	2																		
[50]	1																		
[51]	2																		
[52]	5																		
[53]	2																		
[54]	3																		
[55]	3																		
[56]	1																		
[57]	8																		
[58]	1																		
[59]	9																		
[60]	8																		
[61]	1																		
[62]	1																		
[63]	1																		
[64]	11																		
Summary	221	13	24	26	25	29	5	16	7	5	5	9	18	14	9	4	3	9	9

Table 5. Abbreviations used in table 3

Mitigation	Adaptation
G: General	G: General
I: Infrastructure	I: Infrastructure
E: Energy	M: Management
M: Management	O: Operation
O: Operations	D: Digital
L: Laws	R: Resilience
R: Regulations	F: Finances
F: Finances	P: Politics
P: Politics	
D: Digital*	

Fig. 2. Number of publications per year

2.5 Reports included into the Review

1. Aadil Rasool, M., Khalilpour, K., Rafiee, A., Karimi, I., Madlener, R.: Evaluation of alternative power-to-chemical pathways for renewable energy exports. *Energy Conversion and Management*. 287, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2023.117010>.
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